

HIGH HORIZON TIME_MOTION STATISTICAL ANALYSIS PLAN

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The following document follows the guidelines for statistical analysis plans for observational studies by Hiemstra et al. 2019.(1)

Study title	The impact of heat stress on healthcare workers’ quality of care processes during delivery: a cross-country study using time-motion methods
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2 Background

Providing high-quality care at birth is critical for ensuring the safety of both mothers and newborns. The nature of childbirth, while a physiological process, also presents unique challenges, with health workers have to manage managing a volume of deliveries, and a range of obstetric and neonatal emergencies.

Exposure to excessive environmental heat may exacerbate these pressures, making an already demanding working environment even more difficult for health workers to navigate, especially in resource-limited maternity wards.(2)

Healthcare workers (HCW) frequently experience ambient heat at their workplace, particularly in hot climates with inadequate infrastructure, such as those in high mortality/ morbidity settings of low- and middle-income countries.(3) The heat impact can compromise the HCWs well-being and their performance due to physical exhaustion and dehydration(4). Further, heat may also affect HCWs' ability to concentrate, impairing their clinical decision-making and overall efficiency(5).

Despite increasing awareness of occupational heat stress, most research focuses on outdoor labourers(6), such as construction and agricultural workers, leaving the specific challenges faced by healthcare professionals largely unexplored. Further, the research on heat impact mostly focuses on individual-level outcomes (e.g. heat strain) or system-level indicators (such as absenteeism). However, to date, the literature that has examined the impact of heat on clinical procedures and workflows in healthcare settings is scarce (7,8). This study seeks to address this gap by applying the time-motion study method, enabling detailed analysis of clinical practices and adherence to global quality-of-care (QoC) standards.

This time-motion sub-study is embedded within the HIGH Horizons project, a broader observational study investigating how environmental and occupational factors affect the physical and mental health of maternity healthcare workers in South Africa,

Sweden, and Zimbabwe, as outlined in the main study protocol (version 1.0, 28 March 2023).

This sub-study contributes to the broader HIGH Horizons project and addresses two main aims: one methodological and one analytical.

- Aim 1 is to develop an observational tool, grounded in gold-standard time-motion methods, to accurately assess quality of intrapartum care (9)
- Aim 2 is to examine how heat exposure (heat stress) affects healthcare workers' performance, specifically in terms of adherence to evidence-based processes during childbirth.

This protocol aims to review the key information to investigate statistically the latter aim of the study (aim 2).

3 Objectives

The underlying research hypothesis of this study is that exposure to heat stress - defined as the heat load resulting from the combined contributions of metabolic heat production, environmental factors (such as air temperature, air movement, humidity and radiant heat); and clothing requirements)(10) - may cause a decline (negatively influence) in aspects of health workers (professionals) quality-of-care processes. More specifically, this study aims to:

- Describe the variation of different quality-of-care processes by childbirth characteristics and by heat stress
- Estimate the effect size of direct and short-term heat stress on different quality-of-care processes

4 Study Methods

4.1 Study design

This is a cross-sectional study, conducted in two public hospitals. One is a high-volume, urban district hospital in a metropolitan area of South Africa, serving a catchment population of over 330,000 and managing more than 100 deliveries monthly. The other is a district-level hospital situated in an urban centre of Zimbabwe, with a catchment population exceeding 240,000 and a monthly delivery volume ranging between 160 and 180. Both facilities provide Comprehensive emergency and obstetrics services in resource-constrained settings and were selected to capture diverse climatic and health system contexts relevant to the study objectives.

Clear guidelines for observers were developed and shared during training on how to behave when witnessing situations that could harm mother or newborns.

This study is focused on the 'process' dimension of the Danobedian's model to measure quality of care. The 'Process' includes the care received by patients, including the adherence to standards of care provision(11).

4.2 Power considerations

Given the project resources, we aimed to observe 400 deliveries (200 in each season, one hotter and one cooler) across the two hospitals. With an estimate of 20 healthcare workers in each hospital and 10 events per healthcare worker, we have

80% power (assuming a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$) to detect a minimum effect size (odds ratio) of 2.7 with an ICC of 0.05, and effect size of 3.16 with an ICC of 0.1, and a minimum effect size of 5.46 with an ICC of 0.3. These calculations are based on the formula by Fleiss et al 2003(12) They do not account for varying number of deliveries conducted per health worker which we have experienced, or the effect of any confounder.

The analysis is guided by the hypothesis that exposure to ambient heat will impair the provision of quality care. In other words, healthcare workers exposed to high heat stress are likely to provide fewer evidence-based practices, increased chance of omissions, and increased chance of unrecommended practices that are believed to reduce workload.

4.3 Statistical interim analysis and stopping guidance

Data quality was checked as data were accrued using descriptive statistics to enable the detection of errors during data collection.

No stopping rules were identified as there was not intervention being tested.

4.3.1 Timing of final analysis

All inferential analyses will be carried out after publication of this protocol.

4.4 Timing of outcome assessment

Data was collected between February and September 2024 in South Africa and between October 2023 and July 2024 in Zimbabwe. Access to the full heat stress data will be available from July 2025 for the reference period.

5 STATISTICAL PRINCIPLES

5.1 Confidence intervals and p-values

The findings will be interpreted using a type error level of 5% or below. Effect-size estimates will be reported with 95% Confidence intervals.

5.2 Adherence and Protocol deviations

Deviations from the current protocol will be reported in publications based on this analysis plan. Deviations in terms of outcome definition and fitting models will be key areas to highlight in future data reporting.

6 Study POPULATION

6.1 Screening data

We collected data on deliveries during mornings and afternoon shifts. The observation period was about 6-8 weeks in each season. No data on weekends were collected. A sample of deliveries were observed during the night shift in Zimbabwe, and none in SA due to safety concerns for data collectors.

Data collectors were guided by the hospital healthcare professionals, namely birth attendants(BAs), in order to maximise the number of deliveries observed. More specifically communication focused on understanding where and who would oversee deliveries and hence choose who to observe based on this information. All birth attendants in charge of deliveries were approached to take part in this study. Data collectors were instructed to try and observe each birth attendant in equal amount (time being observed) where possible; and also as many deliveries as possible within

a shift. Each observation session captures the actions of only one birth attendants at any one time.

6.2 Other sources of data

6.2.1 Routine facility-level data

To adjust for differences in workload and staffing level, which can confound the relationship between heat and performance, routine facility-level data will be retrieved. Specifically, data on service volume—captured through the total number of deliveries recorded in the labour and delivery ward each day—and staff volume—reflected by the total number of healthcare workers present in the facility during each day of observation using staff attendance registries—will be extracted from routine registers or facility records.

6.2.2 Questionnaire

As part of the HIGH HORIZON study, the healthcare workers, including birth attendants participating in this study, completed a baseline questionnaire, reporting their age, sex, cadre, educational background and years of experience. We will use these covariates to adjust for differences in those characteristics.

6.2.3 Heat stress data

The wider HIGH HORIZON study collected internal thermal data using portable temperature and humidity loggers placed in indoor work environments to capture ambient thermal conditions during healthcare workers' shifts. These data will be used to generate a heat stress measure for our primary exposure (Wet-Bulb Globe Temperature) (13).

6.3 Eligibility

The unit of analysis is an observation session which covers the intrapartum care provided to a single birthing mother. Intrapartum care refers to the care provided to a woman and her baby during labour and delivery, starting from the onset of regular contractions (proxy for first stage of labour) and continuing until the delivery of the placenta (end of third stage of labour)(14). Observation sessions were limited to vaginal deliveries. We did not observe c-sections. In the event of emergency c-section, we included data from the delivery room up to the point of transfer to the c-section area.

The observers were based only on the labour and delivery ward and, typically, women would come into the delivery room where the observation took place when they were at an advanced first stage of labour or already fully dilated. Hence, we could not effectively observe monitoring of vital signs that usually happen during first stage of labour as this occurred in a separate location (antenatal ward or at home). They were discharged from the delivery cubicle relatively quickly after the third stage of labour. Hence, we could not observe comprehensively some post-partum practices such as breastfeeding that typically happened in a separate postnatal area.

Birth attendants who provided written consent to the observation were included in this study. All labour or delivering women, attended by the birth attendants observed, were in principle eligible to participate as long they provided verbal consent. Hereafter we will refer sometimes to the delivery “being observed” for simplicity; whereas we were actually observing the actions of the birth attendants caring for the woman during delivery.

6.4 Recruitment

All birth attendants in charge of deliveries were approached to consent to the study in the participating hospitals.

6.5 Withdrawal / Follow-up

No withdrawal or drop-outs were recorded after recruitment.

6.6 Baseline participants characteristics

Baseline characteristics of birth attendants and the observed births will be reported. Data on baseline characteristics such as information on the sessions (e.g. length of time observed), information on the deliveries (e.g. complications), information on the birth attendants (e.g. cadre), information on the heat exposure (e.g. range of temperature and humidity).

7 ANALYSIS

7.1 Dataset structure

The unit of analysis is an 'observation session' which covers the process of intrapartum care provided to a single birthing mother. Raw time-motion data feature a series of tasks (actions), with each action given a time-stamp. We transformed the data such that quality-of-care outcomes were aggregated at the session-level using the unique observation session id variable.

We performed further data processing to ensure data consistency. When an observation session included care for two sub-sequent women, the session was split based on the woman being observed. We also captured scenarios where a woman was cared for by more than one healthcare workers consecutively, e.g. when a shift ends and a second healthcare worker takes over the responsibility of giving birth. In these instances, we combined those two sessions into one unit session to ensure that all sessions are similar in that each represents the care provided to one woman, whilst retaining the information on the healthcare workers being observed.

We excluded data in sessions entered erroneously, which we identified by visual inspection. Such data might only have contextual data, with no care processes (clinical procedure or communication). The aim was to verify if they truly belong to an observation session or resulted from human errors. Excluded data will be reported in future dissemination of findings.

7.2 Outcome definitions

Time-motion data features a granular series of time-stamped actions, which enables analysing a range of outcomes. The outcomes in this study are intended to evaluate the impact of ambient heat on the provision quality-of-care processes (11). In this study, the choice of outcomes was based on whether they were considered susceptible to heat exposure based on the consensus of the study investigators.

For the purposes of this study, we distinguish two categories of outcomes based on whether they are tied to a certain event: (i) labour stage-independent outcomes, referring to the occurrence of certain actions irrelevant to the stage of labour; (ii) labour stage-dependent outcomes: the underlying actions only count if they occur within a defined period of time during labour, delivery or post-partum.

Outcomes are defined to reflect different aspects of quality of care processes as detailed by guidance from the WHO guidance documents:

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- WHO Labour Guide User's Manual (15), and
- Standards for improving quality of maternal and newborn care in health facilities(16)

It is important to note that this study focuses on measures of QoC processes (e.g. provision of evidence-based practices), which means the study takes the perspective of provider. Accordingly, investigating QoC outcomes from the perspective of users (e.g. health outcomes and user satisfaction) is not within the scope this study.

7.2.1 Labour Stage-independent outcomes

The first set of outcomes is labour-stage-independent (Table 1). Tasks under these outcomes count into the measure whenever they happen. The period in which outcome-related actions count (hereafter *reference period*) is the entire observation session. Accordingly, regression models for these outcomes will control for the length of the observation, as longer sessions are associated with increased frequency of related actions – see confounding section below.

7.2.2 Labour Stage-dependent outcomes

These outcomes are recorded when they occur at a specific stage of labour. The reference period varies based on the outcome definition. For example, for *Woman left alone* (outcome 8), the reference period is between the active stage of labour and birth. The length of the reference period will be accounted for when modelling these outcomes.

7.2.3 Exposure definition

The study aims to evaluate the impact of heat on quality-of-care processes. Exposure variables include a range of heat stress measures:

Our primary exposure measure is indoor heat stress, captured using wet-bulb globe temperature (WBGT) loggers installed in the labour wards of the two hospitals. Specifically, we use the average WBGT value recorded one hour prior to delivery session

For secondary exposure measures, we will explore indicators that capture both the intensity and duration of heat exposure. These may include: a) the cumulative duration of the shift during which heat stress exceeded a predefined threshold, b) heat stress exposure during the time preceding the shift, for which we will use outdoor data (e.g. ERA-5 reanalysis) (17).

Note on handling missingness in exposure data:

When heat stress data from the labour ward are missing, we will use data from other rooms with similar thermal characteristics.

7.3 Analysis methods

7.3.1 Descriptive analysis

We will provide a summary of the sessions baseline characteristics such as session length, % of complications, % singleton etc. We will calculate the distribution of each outcome and by the key exposures of interest and country.

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7.3.2 Multivariate analysis

We will investigate the association between our heat stress and QoC processes using a regression model.

7.3.2.1 Model choice:

We will employ a mixed-effects model with robust standard errors clustered at the midwife level to account for intra-cluster correlation arising from multiple sessions conducted by the same midwife. The selection and specification of statistical models will be guided by the results of diagnostic tests and goodness-of-fit assessments. If nonlinear models perform better than linear equivalents, we will use Generalised Additive Models to allow for a flexible nonlinear relationship between the outcome and the exposure. Diagnostic tests results for alternative models will be reported.

7.3.3 Other co-variates

We will control for other co-variates in the model including the length of the observation session and other potential confounders including: shift (morning, afternoon, night), country (Zim or SA), complications (e.g. breech delivery, prolonged labour, haemorrhage, pre-eclampsia/eclampsia, birth asphyxia), singleton/ multiple, parity, workload (based on whether the attendant is working alone, and the number of deliveries performed at the facility on the day or shift), number of working hours preceding the delivery (calculated as the difference between the delivery time and beginning of the shift), years of experience, age and cadre. The inclusion of these confounders depends on sufficient variation in these parameters by the outcome and exposure of interest, and tests of collinearity. Further selection of model parameters, including the effect modification of covariates (e.g. country or years of experience) will be determined using goodness of fit tests (e.g. Likelihood ratio test and Akaike Information Criterion).

7.4 Missing data

Due to the nature of time-motion study data, we anticipate that missing data will likely result from observer errors. For example, an observer may fail to tap the button corresponding to the action or labour stage under observation. While it is difficult to discern error patterns, we expect this failure to register to be sporadic, occurring at random and therefore independently of the heat data, impact on data quality will tend to be low.

7.5 Harms

Not applicable, as not intervention implemented.

7.6 Statistical software

STATA SE v18 and R

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9 Appendix

Table 1 Stage independent variables

Processes concerned with the provision of:	Guidance/standard	Definition/Measure and Time-motion items involved	Hypothesis during hot days	Measure	Assumptions or limitations
Respect and preservation of dignity	<p>“5.1 All women and newborns have privacy around the time of labour and childbirth, and their confidentiality is respected.” (16)</p> <p>“5.2 No woman or newborn is subjected to mistreatment, such as physical, sexual or verbal abuse, discrimination, neglect, detainment, extortion or denial of services.” (16)</p>	<p>No verbal or physical Abuse recorded;</p> <p>Birth attendant ensures privacy</p>	Less frequent	Binary, 0,1	NA
Communication	<p>“4.1 All women and their families receive information about the care and have effective interactions with staff.”(16)</p> <p>"Labour Care Guide: Effective communication</p>	<p>BA Takes permission to conduct procedures;</p> <p>Explains procedures;</p> <p>gives general advice</p>	Less frequent	Count	NA

Processes concerned with the provision of:	Guidance/standard	Definition/Measure and Time-motion items involved	Hypothesis during hot days	Measure	Assumptions or limitations
	between maternity care providers and women in labour, using simple and culturally acceptable methods is recommended." (16)				
Providing support	<p>"6.2 Every woman receives support to strengthens her capability during childbirth."(16)</p> <p>Supportive care (Section 2 of the WHO labour care guide)(15)</p>	<p>Encourages hydration;</p> <p>Encourages movement;</p> <p>Offers Pain management</p>	Less frequent	Binary, 0,1	NA
Taking a break	NA	Breaks taken in the room (being observed)	More frequent	Binary, 0,1	NA

Table 2 Stage dependent outcomes

Outcomes	Guidance or standard	Definition/Measure and TM items involved	Hypothesis during hot days	Numerator	Assumptions, limitations & reference periods
Woman left alone in the room	WHO guidelines strongly recommend providing continuous support and monitoring to promote a positive childbirth experience (15)	Left alone in the room from active pushing until newborn is delivered.	More likely for a mother to be alone during active stage due to healthcare workers taking longer breaks.	Binary if ever alone or not	Length of time from active pushing until the baby is born needs to be considered (the first baby is born in case of twins).
Foetal and maternal Monitoring	Sections 3 and 5 of the WHO labour guide	FHR – every 30 minutes during active stage; every 5 minutes during second stage. For the purpose of analysis – at least once Duration of contractions - assess contractions every 30 minutes during the first stage of labour and at least every 15 minutes during the second stage. For the purpose of analysis – at least once	Less frequent	Binary (any), 0,1	Only sessions with a least 30 minutes from start to birth

Outcomes	Guidance or standard	Definition/Measure and TM items involved	Hypothesis during hot days	Numerator	Assumptions, limitations & reference periods
Newborns receive essential routine care immediately after birth.	WHO Standards(16)	Delayed umbilical cord clamping (≥ 1 minutes from birth) Immediate Skin-to-skin Dried (wiping baby)	Less frequent	Binary: all three (complete) vs not completed (less than 3)	Missing means a birth was not recorded as this outcome is limited to sessions where delivery happens Excludes sessions where cord clamping was not recorded/observed (just one session). Limitation: cannot observe whether skin to skin happened outside of the delivery cubicle and several sessions do not last as long as 60 minutes after delivery.
Unrecommended practices to speed up labour	WHO labour guide	Any of the unrecommended practices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fundal Pressure 	Increased	Binary (0,1)	Reference period is during late 1 st stage and 2 nd stage

Outcomes	Guidance or standard	Definition/Measure and TM items involved	Hypothesis during hot days	Numerator	Assumptions, limitations & reference periods
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administering uterotonic to speed up labour • Amniotomy 			Assumption: In sessions where no dilatation was recorded, we assume that the beginning of the session can be used as a starting point

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